

THE ESSENCE AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF "SOCIAL PREVENTION" OF LEGAL VIOLATIONS

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Annotation This article highlights the efforts undertaken in recent years within our country to combat crime. It focuses on the initiative to transform the Republic's mahallas into "green" crime-free zones, based on an in-depth analysis of the criminogenic situation at the grassroots level and the social and domestic issues that have been troubling the population.

Keywords: "social prevention" of offenses, social prevention, prevention inspector, working on "mahallabay", "oilabay" and "fuqarobay" levels, concept of social prevention, "Temir daftar", "Ayollar daftari" and "Yoshlar daftari."

The peace and tranquility of a country depend on the elimination of socio-economic problems, the formation of citizens' legal culture, and ensuring the rule of law. Furthermore, implementing early prevention of offenses, identifying and eliminating their causes and conditions that enable their occurrence, and creating an effective system for these measures are crucial not only for maintaining peace but also for the prosperity of the state and society.

Today, early prevention of offenses has become the primary focus in the field of combating crime. In this regard, we can see the ideological thoughts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who stated, "Offenses do not occur by themselves. The main issue is not fighting against the consequences of offenses, but rather their early prevention and timely elimination of the causes and conditions that allow them to be committed."

Moreover, systematic efforts are being undertaken to ensure that the mahalla serves as a reliable "bridge" between the population and government bodies, and to create the necessary conditions for our people to lead peaceful and tranquil lives.

In this regard, the establishment of the "mahalla seven" system, based on the principle of "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla," plays a crucial role in identifying and comprehensively addressing problems in each mahalla. This system is significant in detecting individuals with a high risk of committing crimes or becoming victims, preventing offenses early by resolving their socio-economic issues, and maintaining a stable criminogenic situation in the mahallas of the republic.

As is known, internal affairs bodies play a significant role in crime prevention, and the main responsibilities in this area are assigned to them. Prevention (senior) inspectors at the support points of internal affairs bodies are among the key entities ensuring the implementation of these tasks in mahallas.

Today, the prevention (senior) inspectors of the internal affairs bodies' support points, in collaboration with the "mahalla seven," are implementing preventive measures in mahallas to identify and address the social and domestic problems of individuals with a high likelihood of committing offenses or becoming victims of offenses.

Based on the analysis, it should be noted that in 2024, prevention inspectors identified a total of 587,500 social prevention cases, issued conclusions for them, of which 70 percent, or 410,000, received assistance, had their problems resolved, and joint conclusions were drawn up.

Analysis of social and preventive measures by region in 2024:

In the Tashkent region, 31 percent or 22,111 out of 70,516 social prevention cases, in the city of Tashkent - 57 percent or 14,477 out of 25,591, in the Samarkand region - 60.1 percent or 20,439 out of 34,032, in the Andijan region - 63.8 percent or 32,132 out of 50,334, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan - 54 percent or 14,817 out of 23,122, in the Bukhara region - 66.1 percent or 21,635 out of 32,726, in the Syrdarya region - 68.5 percent or 31,683 out of 46,282 had their problems resolved and joint conclusions were drawn up.

The implementation of crime prevention undoubtedly constitutes "social prevention" of these offenses. It should be especially noted that today in the social life of our country, a system has been established for identifying and addressing the socio-economic problems of citizens on an individual, family, and neighborhood level. Additionally, a number of measures are being implemented to provide social support to individuals in difficult social and living conditions, those who are unemployed, lack a permanent source of income, and need social assistance by including them in the "Temir daftar," "Ayollar daftari," "Yoshlar daftari," "Neighborhood Notebook," "Disabled People's Notebook," and "Unified Register of Social Protection (URSP)."

The introduction of the "fuqarobay", "oilabay" and "mahallabay" system for addressing the problems of the population in Uzbekistan was first announced by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a video conference meeting on January 27, 2021.

In this regard, the Head of State emphasized: "Now, when organizing work on a neighborhood basis, the chairman of the mahalla, the prevention inspector, the school principal, and the youth leader will identify the problems of young people on an individual basis. From now on, we will work with citizens individually in the mahalla. What is the mood of the person inside the house? What are their goals and aspirations? What problems do they have? They must identify these issues on a person-by-person basis and present clear and concise matters before the responsible leaders."

Indeed, it is crucial to understand the essence, goals, and objectives of this "fuqarobay", "oilabay" and "mahallabay" approach, as well as to determine its place and significance in the social life of our country.

The "mahallabay" system involves activities to identify and eliminate existing problems that negatively affect the lifestyle of citizens living in the mahalla. For example, it includes a system of measures implemented to address shortcomings in providing the mahalla population with drinking water, gas, and electricity, addressing malfunctions in the road infrastructure of the mahalla, and improving the organization of household services for residents.

The "oilabay" work system focuses on identifying and addressing existing problems within families. These issues have a similar negative impact on the lifestyle of family members living together, causing deterioration in social relations between them and undermining their stability. This process involves addressing problems that negatively affect family members' lifestyles, including allocating land considering their housing needs and providing practical assistance in obtaining housing through preferential loans.

The "fuqarobay" working system provides practical assistance to individuals in solving problems specifically related to them. For example, it includes measures to assist citizens, including unorganized youth, in studying and finding employment, vocational training, providing practical help in assigning benefits to persons with disabilities and obtaining wheelchairs, guiding them towards private entrepreneurship and small businesses, and assisting them in obtaining preferential loans.

We can observe that the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 27 dated November 29, 2021, "On Approving the Concept of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Measures for its Implementation," in Appendix 2, which approved the "Strategy for the Development of the Public Security System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025," has given a task in paragraph 77 to introduce "social prevention" as a type of crime prevention and define specific mechanisms for its application in our country.

However, according to Article 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention" dated May 14, 2014, there are four types of crime prevention:

1) general prevention of offenses; 2) special prevention of offenses; 3) individual prevention of offenses; 4) victimological prevention of offenses.

Nevertheless, "social prevention," mentioned in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-27 dated November 29, 2021, has not been introduced as a type of crime prevention. In this regard, the scientific and theoretical foundations of social prevention of offenses have not been sufficiently studied in our country. This limits the possibility of ensuring the effectiveness of early prevention of offenses.

Today, before discussing the concept of "social prevention of offenses," which is considered one of the main measures for identifying individuals with a high likelihood of committing offenses or becoming victims of offenses and addressing their social and domestic problems, we believe it is necessary to clarify the concepts of "offense" and "social prevention," which form the basis of this concept.

It should also be emphasized that developing a new scientific concept for implementing social prevention of offenses and continuously advancing reforms in this process, as well as improving legislative norms for this purpose, should be closely linked with political, economic, and legal reforms in our country.

According to some sources, the concept of prevention primarily includes scientifically based and timely actions aimed at:

- preventing potential physical, mental, or socio-cultural conflicts in individuals and at-risk groups;
- maintaining, supporting, and protecting people's normal standard of living and health;
- assisting them in achieving their goals and realizing their inner potential.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our legislation, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention" on May 14, 2014, ensured the legislative consolidation of the legal definition of the concept of "offense."

According to the law, an "offense" is defined as a culpable, unlawful act (action or inaction) for which administrative or criminal liability is provided (Article 3).

In our opinion, social prevention is not a concept that emerged recently. Since ancient times, issues of crime and criminal personality, their origins and formation, harmful consequences for society, and the reduction of these consequences have been studied by humanity as a social reality, and various opinions and views have been formed regarding their

content. The essence of this process can be understood by examining the origins of "social prevention."

In the course of our research, we attempted to analyze the concept of "social prevention" within the framework of the following approaches.

The first approach: the views of scientists in this field have attempted to reveal the essence of the concept of "social prevention."

Russian scientists A.S. Blankova and I.A. Burmistrova defined the concept of social prevention as "conscious, purposeful, socially organized activity aimed at preventing potential social, psychological-pedagogical, legal, and other problems and achieving the expected result."

In the research of A.F. Basov and N.F. Basova, social prevention is defined as "a system of social measures aimed at maintaining and protecting people's normal standard of living, as well as preventing social deviations by eliminating the causes and conditions of their occurrence."

In our opinion, approaches in both directions should activate systems and structures capable of preventing potential problems or solving the set tasks. An important principle of social prevention is that assistance to people should be provided based on their social and physical condition.

K.R. Abdurasulova, in contrast to the above definition, provides a broader and more comprehensive definition of general social prevention. In her opinion, "General social prevention encompasses socio-political, o

In our opinion, the following aspects of this definition cannot be agreed upon: 1) "re-educating violators of social moral rules" is part of the goal of individual, not general prevention; 2) the definition should reflect the areas to which prevention is directed, namely socio-political, organizational, legal and educational measures.

However, according to L.P. Kuznetsova, social prevention is "a conscious, purposeful, socially organized activity aimed at preventing potential social, psychological-pedagogical, legal, and other problems and achieving the expected result."

According to lawyer P. Ya. Sitkilov, social prevention is "a systematic and timely influence aimed at maintaining the functional state of a social object and preventing all types of negative processes in its vital activity. Social prevention is an activity aimed at preventing the emergence, spread, and intensification of negative social phenomena and their dangerous consequences."

In our opinion, the above definition of the concept of "social prevention" allows us to highlight the main goals aimed at achieving this process.

Firstly, identifying the causes and conditions contributing to the emergence of any problem or complex of problems;

Secondly, reducing or preventing the possibility of unacceptable changes in the system of social standards and norms in the activities and behavior of an individual or group;

Thirdly, preserving, supporting, and protecting the optimal standard of living and lifestyle of people;

Fourthly, assisting an individual or group in achieving set goals, revealing their inner potential and creative abilities.

Even a superficial analysis of the listed goals allows us to conclude that under certain conditions, any person, any social group, organization, or community may need social and preventive measures, regardless of their current level of social well-being.

In this regard, as L.V. Topchiy notes, social prevention is "a scientifically based and timely influence to preserve the functional state of the social object and prevent possible negative processes in its vital activity."

However, D.N. Marikin and V.S. Yakumchuk view the concept of "social prevention" (prevention, precaution) as an activity to maintain the level of social resilience by preventing social problems and social disorders or eliminating their causes. Social prevention is aimed at preventing physical, mental, or socio-cultural conflicts that may arise in individuals and "risk groups," preserving, supporting, and protecting people's normal lifestyle and health, helping them achieve their goals and unlock their inner potential.

In our opinion, social prevention creates the basis for the process of normal socialization of the individual, based on the priority of the principles of legality and morality. Therefore, one can agree with the opinion of several researchers on social prevention problems that the entire population needs social prevention.

As can be seen, there are also population groups that need it more. These are children, adolescents, and individuals leading immoral lives. A modern approach to social prevention involves abandoning the previous medical model, which was aimed only at treating the disease, i.e., providing assistance. Today, it is important to identify the causes of the disease, that is, the social and psychological factors that caused the negative consequences.

According to E.I. Kholostova, social prevention is "one of the directions of social policy, implemented through the adoption of relevant laws, the activities of educational institutions, healthcare, social labor, culture, mass media, etc. The goal of social prevention is not only to prevent negative phenomena and problems but also to create conditions for the full functioning of society. The main directions of prevention are the identification, neutralization, or elimination of factors that cause a particular negative phenomenon, contribute to their renewal, and hinder human development."

The above-mentioned scientists believe that prevention in the implementation of "social prevention" is an important means of combating development in the early stages of any negative processes. This allows for easing the burden of social problems at a lower cost and steering the process in a more favorable direction. In modern conditions, the importance of not only identifying problems of various levels but also eliminating them implies, first and foremost, the prevention of these complex situations.

In our opinion, these approaches by scholars do not fully reveal the content of "social prevention." The reason is that they have not paid sufficient attention to the issue of developing and implementing measures to eliminate the causes and conditions of offenses, as well as to prevent them. However, it can also be concluded that "social prevention" encompasses "social prevention of offenses." But the point here is not simply to determine which of them is a broader or narrower concept, but to clarify the scope and purpose of these concepts through this analysis.

The second approach: "social prevention" of offenses when studying and analyzing the legislation of national and foreign countries;

In the regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the new edition of the Constitution has tripled the norms related to the state's obligations in the social sphere. Most

importantly, for the first time, Article 1 of the Basic Law was supplemented with the norm "Uzbekistan is a sovereign, democratic, legal, social, and secular state with a republican form of government." In particular, Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "Everyone has the right to social security in old age, in case of disability, unemployment, as well as in case of loss of a breadwinner and in other cases provided for by law," Article 57 states: "The rights of disabled and lonely elderly people, persons with disabilities and other socially vulnerable categories of the population are under state protection." The existence of such norms serves to protect the rights and freedoms of persons in need of social protection.

A social state is understood, first of all, as a state that guarantees its citizens a certain minimum level of well-being. It was emphasized that the main goal of the New Uzbekistan is to care for every citizen, ensure inclusive development, and equal rights and opportunities for all segments of the population.

However, although "social prevention of offenses" was not interpreted as a specific concept until 2023, the measures applied for its implementation are reflected in the following regulatory legal acts.

For example, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2017 No. PP-2833 "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Crime Prevention and Combating Crime" defines measures applied to vulnerable segments of the population and persons with a high probability of committing offenses:

"increasing the effectiveness of measures to address social problems of the population, primarily ensuring their employment, activating the involvement of women and youth in socially useful activities, and meaningful organization of the leisure time of minors;

developing a system of measures to provide legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical, and other assistance to victims of offenses and persons with antisocial behavior, prone to committing or having committed offenses" as measures of "social prevention" of offenses.

Appendix 1 to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 No. PP-5050 "On Additional Organizational Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime" The Regulation on the Mahalla Law Enforcement Point also defines the main task of the mahalla law enforcement point as "solving the problems of the population, as well as organizing work on the social adaptation of victims of offenses, persons with antisocial behavior, persons who have committed offenses" for the implementation of "social prevention" measures with persons who have committed offenses or are at high risk of becoming victims of offenses.

For the first time, the concept of "social prevention" of offenses in our country was defined in the instruction approved by the joint resolution of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction, and the Ministry of Youth Policy and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 30, 2023, No. 10/3qq/05qq. The concept of "social prevention" is defined as a set of measures aimed at providing legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical, and other types of assistance to persons prone to committing offenses or with a high probability of becoming victims of offenses, as well as instilling in them the norms and rules of behavior accepted in society.

However, Resolution No. 801 of November 30, 2024 by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Increase the Effectiveness of the Social Prevention System in Mahallas Based on the Principle of 'Prosperous and Safe Mahalla'" provides for strengthening social prevention work in mahallas. The peculiarity of this document is that while the resolution defines various measures of social prevention, it does not give a clear, official definition of the term "social prevention." This, in turn, leads to various interpretations of social prevention, as people do not know exactly what it means. This results in a lack of unified standards.

Additionally, in Article 3 of the draft Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. QL-341/23-3 "On Crime Prevention," which has been uploaded to the Unified Electronic System for the Development and Coordination of Regulatory Legal Acts, "social crime prevention" is included as a basic concept. The draft law defines the concept of "social prevention of offenses" as follows: This, in turn, leads to various interpretations of social prevention, not knowing what it means.

"Social prevention of offenses is a set of preventive measures carried out among persons suffering from drug addiction, mental disorders, tuberculosis, sexually transmitted diseases, HIV infection, or who, as a result of neglect or lack of supervision, are in conditions dangerous to their life or health, or do not meet the requirements for maintenance, upbringing, or education, or are prone to committing offenses or other antisocial acts."

In the aforementioned draft Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention," uploaded to the Unified Electronic System for the Development and Coordination of Regulatory Legal Acts, the newly introduced concept of social prevention of offenses mainly refers to measures carried out among persons registered with medical institutions, unsupervised and neglected minors, as well as persons prone to committing antisocial acts. However, it does not target socially vulnerable segments of the population, persons prone to committing offenses as a result of social problems, or those with a high probability of becoming victims of offenses.

In the regulatory legal acts of the Russian Federation - In several countries, particularly in higher and secondary specialized (legal specialty) educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Russian Federation, starting from the 1978/1979 academic year, the subject was renamed "Prevention of Offenses" to clarify its purpose. At the same time, the issue of organizing management in the prevention of offenses remained part of its content. Subsequently, this subject was also called "Criminology and Social Prevention."

As a result of the reforms carried out in the Russian Federation, in the first quarter of the 21st century, large-scale implementation of "social prevention" measures began to be applied mainly in the fields of medicine and crime prevention. "Social prevention" is defined as a set of specific social measures (economic, organizational, managerial, cultural, educational, etc.) carried out to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to illegal actions, with the aim of preventing offenses and reducing their number until their complete elimination.

Comprehensive planning of "social prevention" is one of the main forms of coordinating the activities of state bodies, economic entities, public organizations, and labor collectives in this area. This involves the joint development of coordinated plans to combat crime, which provides for a system of long-term or permanent measures to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions for the commission of illegal acts by various bodies, organizations, and

groups, and to exert an educational influence on offenders. As a result, a foundation is created for mutual cooperation between all participants in preventive measures to combat offenses and their most dangerous type - crime.

Comprehensive planning of "social prevention" is one of the main forms of coordinating the activities of state, economic bodies, public organizations, and labor collectives in this area. This is the joint development of coordinated plans to combat crime, which provides for a system of long-term or permanent measures to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions for the commission of illegal acts by various bodies, organizations, and groups, and to exert an educational influence on offenders. As a result, a foundation will be created for mutual cooperation between all participants in preventive measures to combat offenses and their most dangerous type - crime.

In the regulatory legal acts of South African countries, the concept of "social prevention" is defined in a completely different way compared to their legislation. "Social prevention" in these countries refers to the prevention of social crimes. "Social prevention" is understood as initiatives and strategies aimed at preventing social crimes, eliminating the root causes of crime, and preventing its occurrence through social, economic, and political changes.

At that time, "social prevention" in South African countries included the implementation of political programs aimed at eliminating structural and ideological factors leading to crime. The prevention of social crimes can be assessed as a transformative approach that requires significant resources and time to achieve success. It also recognizes the need for spatial differences and adapted approaches in various regions as a result of the justice system. Technology is seen as a potential tool for addressing problems related to targeted geography and crime prevention.

In Belgium's regulatory legal acts, "social prevention" - the prevention of social crimes - is developing within the framework of a policy to eliminate national and local offenses, which has a historical basis. This process is influenced by political ideologies and institutional structures. The restorative model of criminal justice is considered a social approach to combating crime, as it strengthens ties with society and allows for effective responses to crimes.

In Belgium, the prevention of social crimes has been a key concept in the fight against crime and violence, but there are opinions that the state does not support this activity. The government's current rhetoric on crime emphasizes law enforcement measures, and questions exist about the main obstacles to preventing social crimes. The creation and use of information is identified as a weakness in crime prevention efforts in Belgium, and the need for increased government accountability and addressing human rights and democracy issues has been recognized.

In the regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Ukraine - specifically the State Social Security Code - the concept of "social prevention" is defined as a measure aimed at identifying immoral and illegal behavior among families, minors, and youth in difficult life situations, as well as any negative impact on their life and health, and preventing the spread of socially dangerous diseases.

In Japan's regulatory legal acts, crime prevention is aimed not only at punishment but also at preventing the commission of crimes. This concept of social prevention covers all segments of society - schools, families, local communities, police, and government organizations. The National Strategy for Crime Prevention

This document, prepared jointly by the Ministry of Justice, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the National Police Agency of Japan, defines the main priorities for crime prevention. It focuses on reducing offenses among young people, reducing repeat offenses, strengthening cooperation with the public, and addressing social problems (unemployment, homelessness, domestic violence). Police policies on crime prevention: The Japanese police work closely with local populations through the "Kōban" system, implementing preventive measures and disseminating information aimed at crime prevention.

Third approach: Examining the etymology of the concept "social prevention" in its lexical meaning reveals that the term "prevention" is borrowed from medicine and refers to measures to prevent the emergence and spread of diseases that contribute to public health. In dictionaries, the term "prevention" is often interpreted in the sense of "warning."

Prevention is also a set of preemptive measures aimed at maintaining and strengthening the normal state of law and order, and also means "forestalling."

It is known that in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," although "social prevention" is not defined separately, the concept of "social" is interpreted as "related to society, connected with society, public, pertaining to people's relations in society." Usually, the studied objects are classified or categorized for easier or deeper examination.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, we can see that the concept of "social" often conveys a specific meaning when combined with additional auxiliary phrases. For example, we can cite numerous phrases such as "social protection," "social situation," "social adaptation," "social assistance," "social worker," "social partnership," "social survey," and so on. In practical application, this task allows for determining activity directions and achieving proper work organization.

Thus, based on the information presented in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, it can be said that the concept of "social" is derived from the English word "social," and when directly translated into Uzbek, it means "related to the community, society," "pertaining to the life of an individual and society," "social system," "social development," "social production," "social relations." The concept of "social" encompasses terms like social assistance and social protection.

In the encyclopedic dictionary of the Russian social work field, social prevention is defined as "a socially organized activity carried out consciously, with a specific goal, to prevent potential social, psychological-pedagogical, legal, and other problems and to achieve the desired outcome."

All the aforementioned work aims to eliminate and prevent various contradictions in society, as well as ensure social justice and equality. This, in turn, guarantees the early prevention of offenses.

Indeed, these approaches serve to develop measures for the social prevention of offenses in society and ensure their strict, principled, and targeted implementation and effectiveness. Therefore, it is advisable to study the "social orientation theory," which examines the causes of offenses, from the perspective of social prevention of offenses and to form its scientific and theoretical foundations.

In general, we consider it appropriate to study the concepts of "social prevention" and "social prevention of offenses" as closely related but distinct concepts.

In our opinion, it is advisable to define the concept of "social prevention" as follows:

"Social prevention is an activity aimed at eliminating the emergence of socio-economic and other problems among vulnerable segments of the population and individuals in need of social assistance."

Social prevention has preventive properties and ensures the resolution of social problems that have not yet arisen but can be predicted in advance. If sufficient social research and serious forecasting had been conducted before the country's reforms, it would have been possible to prevent the emergence of homelessness, poverty, high mortality rates, and other social problems.

"Social prevention of offenses" is a system of measures aimed at providing social, economic, legal, psychological, medical, pedagogical, and other types of assistance to individuals prone to committing offenses as a result of social problems or with a high probability of becoming victims of offenses.

Therefore, we consider it appropriate to conclude that "social prevention" is an activity in a broad sense, while "social prevention of offenses" is a system of measures existing within this activity.

The ambiguity and contradiction in the concepts used can also be observed in the use of the term "social prevention," which has been widely employed recently in public life, law enforcement practice, and regulatory legal acts.

Based on the foregoing, proposals for improving the theoretical, legal, and practical aspects of "social prevention" of offenses:

1) The following amendments and additions are proposed to the Law "On Crime Prevention" dated May 14, 2014:

1.1. Introduce the following definition of "social prevention" of offenses into Article 3 of the Law, that is, among the basic concepts;

"social prevention" of offenses - a system of measures aimed at providing social, economic, legal, psychological, medical, pedagogical, and other types of assistance to persons prone to committing offenses as a result of social problems or with a high likelihood of becoming victims of offenses.

1.2. Include "social prevention of offenses" in Article 6 of the Law as a separate type of offense prevention;

1.3. Introduce Chapter 61 of the Law as a separate new chapter, providing for "Social Prevention of Offenses";

1.4. Introduce Article 451 of the Law as a separate new article providing for "Measures of Social Prevention of Offenses."

In conclusion, it should be noted that today transforming internal affairs bodies into a people-oriented professional structure and ensuring every internal affairs officer serves in the interests of the people is of utmost importance. Therefore, if prevention inspectors turn their areas into crime-free zones and implement social prevention measures with people from various backgrounds, the intended goal will be achieved and employment of the population will be ensured. This, in turn, will significantly reduce the commission of crimes or offenses and yield positive results. In New Uzbekistan, employees of internal affairs bodies, especially prevention inspectors who are closest to the people, face important tasks. Effective fulfillment of these tasks requires not only professional skills and extensive experience but also deep legal knowledge. The aforementioned decrees and resolutions of the President serve to meet

these needs. Moreover, only comprehensively trained prevention inspectors can be true representatives of the mahalla in the internal affairs bodies, as stated by the head of our state.

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